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APPLICATION SOFTWARE AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS

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ПРИКЛАДНОЕ ПРОГРАММНОЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ И ЕГО ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ

Abstract.

The article reveals the essence of the concept of "means of new information technologies. The possibilities of new information technology tools (NITT) are listed. The place of applied software packages among the means of information technology is especially noted. The names of scientists-researchers who have left a scientific legacy in the creation of applied software are brought to the attention of readers. Teaching staff in the educational process The basic didactic requirements for applied software are revealed.

Аннотация.

В статье раскрыта суть понятия "средства новых информационных технологий. Перечислены возможности СНИТ. Особо отмечено место пакетов прикладных программных средств среди средств информационных технологий. Упомянули имена ученых-исследователей, которые оставили научное наследие в создании прикладных программных средств. Доведена до внимания читателей педагогическая целесообразность использования ППС в учебном процессе. Выявлены основные дидактические требования к прикладным программным средствам.

Keywords: applied software, means of new information technologies, application software requirements.

Ключевые слова: прикладные программные средства, средства новых информационных технологий, требования к ППС.

The implementation of information technologies in the learning process occurs using its specific tools, which in the pedagogical literature are called "Tools of new information technologies (SNIT)". According to Robert I.V., [4] SNIT should be understood as "hardware and software tools and devices operating on the basis of microprocessor computing technology, as well as modern means and information exchange systems that provide collection operations, production, accumulation, storage, processing, transmission of information" [5].

The capabilities of SNIT and the range of tasks solved with their use make it possible to formulate the pedagogical goals of using SNIT in the system of secondary and higher education. These include :

- development of the student's personality (development of thinking, aesthetic education, development of communication abilities;
- formation of information culture); implementation of the social order caused by the informatization of society.

Intensification of all levels of the educational process (especially deepening interdisciplinary connections through the use of modern information processing tools, including audio-video information, when solving problems in various subject areas).

Achieving the goals formulated above is impossible without resolving the issue of determining the main directions for introducing SNIT into the training and education system. This problem is complex in nature and information technology tools can be used as a teaching tool, a cognition tool, a means of developing the learner's personality, an object of study, a means of automating the control and processing of an experiment.

Among the above-mentioned information technology tools, one of the important places is occupied by packages of applied programs for educational purposes, which are called teaching software - applied software. So, teaching staff is understood as an application program designed to organize and support educational dialogue

user with a computer; The functional purpose of teaching staff is to provide educational information and guide training. The problems of developing and using teaching staff are based on a number of theoretical provisions representing: the pedagogical feasibility of using teaching staff; functional purpose of certain types of teaching staff used for training purposes; typology of teaching staff mainly for methodological purposes; requirements for teaching staff used in the educational process.

The pedagogical feasibility of using teaching staff in the educational process is determined by the goals of developing the individual's personality and is based on the methodological purpose of teaching staff. The methodological purpose of teaching staff is determined by the need to intensify the learning process and transfer it to a qualitatively higher level. The most significant, from the perspective of didactic teaching principles, are the following methodological goals, which are most effectively achieved using teaching staff:

- individualization and differentiation of the learning process;
- implementation of control with feedback;
- freeing up study time by performing on a computer labor-intensive computational work;
- computer visualization of educational information;
- modeling and simulation of studied objects and processes or phenomena;
- strengthening learning motivation;
- equipping the student with a strategy for mastering educational material;
- formation of a culture of educational activities, information culture of the student and the teacher.

Having clarified the methodological goals and functions of teaching staff in the pedagogical process, it is necessary to determine the requirements for teaching staff, i.e. those characteristics that will allow the successful development and use of these software tools. Requirements for teaching staff are considered from various points of view. Methodological requirements for teaching staff are formulated in the works of B.S. Gershunsky [3], E.I. Mashbits [4], N.F. Talyzina [8]; psychological requirements were developed by Yu.D. Babaeva and co-author E.I. Mashbits [5]. An analysis of the pedagogical practice of using teaching staff allows us to conclude that the most significant reasons for the creation of low-quality (from a pedagogical point of view) computer programs are: partial and sometimes complete ignorance of didactic principles of teaching during their development; unlawful transfer of traditional forms and methods of teaching to new technology learning using a computer.

At present, no one doubts the fact that in the conditions of informatization of education, the paradigm of pedagogical science is changing, the structure and content of education is changing. New teaching methods, based on active, independent forms of acquiring knowledge and working with information, are replacing demonstration and illustrative-explanatory methods, widely used by traditional teaching methods focused on mainly on the collective perception of information. In parallel, there is a process of using teaching staff to support traditional teaching methods. At the same time, teaching staff used for educational purposes are transferred to some extent to teaching functions, therefore, each program should be built in accordance with the didactic principles of teaching that determine the didactic requirements for teaching staff. It is known that the technique.

The teaching of each academic subject, in turn, takes into account the uniqueness and characteristics of the corresponding science, therefore it is legitimate to talk about methodological requirements for teaching staff, which provide for the specifics and originality of each specific science and the corresponding academic subject. When determining pedagogical requirements for teaching staff, it is also necessary to take into account the rationale for choosing a topic for teaching staff, justified by certain methodological goals, and to ensure verification of the pedagogical effectiveness of using teaching staff.

In addition, it is necessary to take into account the ergonomic and technical requirements for the content and design of teaching staff.

Based on the analysis of the requirements for teaching staff, we can conclude that when developing educational software, great attention should be paid to ensuring that the teaching technology used is adequate to the processes of assimilation of information by students. It should be remembered that combined models of presenting material increase the depth of information processing in the student's brain, thereby ensuring the effectiveness of learning, but excessively detailed presentation attracts information that is unnecessary for a given topic, which the student already possesses, and interferes with the assimilation of the required information. When developing PPP, it is necessary to take into account its use on computer lesson.

This raises the problem of constructing a computer lesson sequence from the point of view of finding the optimal number of program fragments (course frames) that need to be given to the student and how many questions to ask him during the presentation of the theoretical material. In teaching staff, this problem should be implemented in the form of control, which consists in organizing timely assistance to the student when difficulties arise in working with educational material. The main principle for implementing this problem is the principle of interactivity of teaching staff, which is determined by the following factors:

a) allow the student to determine the sequence (course) of the lesson in the case when the content is familiar to him or there are minor difficulties in understanding; provide control to the trainee (if he chooses control, then within the control there is strict guidance from the program);

b) use curriculum designs as alternatives to the linear structure, adapting to individual characteristics and needs;

c) ensure the sensitivity of branching to the presentation of educational information, both to the questions and examples given to each student, and to take into account the time of demonstration of educational material required for each student individually. For example, a student who has made a large number of errors when answering questions does not need an even larger number of questions to understand, but simply a longer time to read and think about the educational material.

List of used literature:

1. Musayev V.H., İsmayılov M.A., Əbilov K.Ə. İnformatika. Ali məktəb üçün dərs vəsaiti, Bakı -2011 il.
2. H.N.Tağiyev, M.A.İsmayılov, C.O.Nəbiyeva, İnformatikanın nəzəri və praktiki əsasları, II hissə, Bakı-2007
3. Gershunsky B.S. Computerization in Education: Problems and prospects. - M.: Pedagogy, 1987. - 246 p.
4. Mashbits E.I. Computerization of education: problems and prospects. -M., 1986.-80s.
5. Mashbits E.I. Design guidelines training programs. - Kyiv., 1986. - 110 p.
6. Robert I.V. Modern information technologies in education: didactic problems, prospects for use. - M.: "School-Press", 1994.-205 p.
7. Robert I.V. Theoretical foundations of creation and use means of informatization of education. dis. ... Dr. ped. Sci. - M., 1994 -339c
8. Talyzina N.F. Methodology for compiling training programs. - M., 1980.-47s.